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The Density and Relevance of Museum Heritage in the Italian Regions During the Period 2017-2021

It decreased by -10.02% between 2017 and 2021

Istat calculates the value of the density and relevance of the museum heritage. The variable is defined as the number of permanent exhibition structures per 100 km², i.e. museums, archaeological areas and monuments open to the public, weighted by the number of visitors. The weight of each structure is assumed to be equal to V_i/VM , where V_i is the number of visitors to the structure, M the total structures and V the total visitors.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of density and relevance of museum heritage in 2021. Lazio is in first place for value of density and relevance of museum heritage in 2021 with an amount of 4.09 units, followed by Campania with 3.58 and from Tuscany with 3.28 units. In the middle of the table are Emilia Romagna with 1.21, Trentino Alto Adige with 1.19 units and Piedmont with 1.18 units. Molise closes the ranking with 0.19 units, followed by Basilicata with 0.18 units and Abruzzo with 0.16 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in the density and relevance of the museum heritage between 2017 and 2021. Umbria is in first place for the value of the density and relevance of the museum heritage between 2017 and 2021 with a value equal to +94.44% corresponding to a variation from 0.72 units up to 1.4 units. Marche follows with a value equal to +43.1% corresponding to a variation from 0.58 units up to 0.83 units. And Molise with a value equal to +35.71% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 0.14 up to 0.19 units. Trentino Alto Adige is mid-table with a value of 9.17% corresponding to a variation from 1.09 units to 1.19 units. Lombardy follows with a value equal to +1.29% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 1.55 units up to 1.57 units. In eleventh place is Piedmont with a variation of 0.00%. In the last places there is Puglia with a variation equal to -27.03% corresponding to a variation from 0.37 units up to 0.27 units corresponding to a variation of -0.2 units. Liguria follows with a variation equal to -37.8% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 1.27 units up to 0.79 units. Lazio closes with a variation of -43.19% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 7.2 units to 4.09 units.

Density and relevance of museum heritage in the Italian macro-regions between 2017 and 2021. The value of the density and relevance of museum heritage had a fluctuating trend between 2017 and 2021. There are two areas of the country characterized by a growth in variable analyzed i.e. Islands with +5.97% and North-East with +0.71%. There are two Italian macro-areas characterized by an invariance in the value of the density and relevance of the museum heritage, namely the North and the South with a variation of 0.00%. There are three macro-areas which are instead characterized by a reduction in the value of the observed variable, namely the North-West with -1.49%, the South with -3.37% and the Center with -26.36%. There are significant differences between the South and the

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Centre-North in terms of density and relevance of the museum heritage. Specifically, the value of the variable observed in the South is 39.00% lower than in the North-West, 42.00% lower than the North, 44.00% lower than the North-East and 72.00% lower than the Center Italy.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified as indicated below:

- Cluster 1: Umbria, Marche, Sicily, Emilia Romagna, Trentino Alto Adige, Calabria, Puglia, Piedmont, Liguria, Basilicata, Valle d'Aosta, Molise, Abruzzo, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lombardy, Veneto;
- Cluster 2: Lazio, Tuscany, Campania.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters calculated considering the average value of the density and relevance of the museum heritage, it appears that $C2 > C1$. We can see that Cluster 2 is made up of only three regions, namely Lazio, Tuscany and Campania. These regions constitute a dominant cluster with average values 4 or 5 times higher than the average value of the regions of Cluster 1. Certainly there are regions that could also be included in cluster 2. However, it is probable that there were no significant investments in museum assets. For example, one of these regions is Veneto.

Conclusions. The value of the density and relevance of museum heritage in the Italian regions decreased between 2017 and 2021. Specifically, the average value decreased by 10.02%. The analysis of the macro-regions shows that the South has a very low value of density and relevance of the museum heritage compared to the other central-northern macro-regions. The clustering highlights that the dominant cluster consists of Lazio, Campania and Tuscany.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Macro-Regioni	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Nord	1,37	1,42	1,35	1,17	1,37
Nord-ovest	1,34	1,31	1,3	1,12	1,32
Nord-est	1,41	1,52	1,4	1,21	1,42
Centro	3,87	3,63	3,92	2,88	2,85
Mezzogiorno	0,8	0,89	0,79	0,68	0,8
Sud	0,89	0,98	0,86	0,75	0,86
Isole	0,67	0,75	0,68	0,59	0,71

Regione	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Piemonte	1,18	1,17	1,08	1,05	1,18
Valle d'Aosta	1,13	0,97	1,05	1,37	1,38
Liguria	1,27	1,14	1,09	0,68	0,79
Lombardia	1,55	1,53	1,61	1,25	1,57
Trentino-Alto Adige	1,09	1,13	1,01	1,16	1,19
Veneto	2,01	2,4	2	1,49	1,82
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	1,51	1,37	1,41	1,36	1,51
Emilia-Romagna	1,07	1,09	1,15	0,97	1,21
Toscana	3,87	3,92	3,94	3,35	3,28
Umbria	0,72	0,81	0,65	0,87	1,4
Marche	0,58	0,65	0,81	0,94	0,83
Lazio	7,2	6,25	7,2	4,31	4,09
Abruzzo	0,13	0,11	0,14	0,16	0,16
Molise	0,14	0,1	0,14	0,25	0,19
Campania	3,63	4,24	3,61	3,11	3,58
Puglia	0,37	0,31	0,29	0,2	0,27
Basilicata	0,16	0,18	0,23	0,18	0,18
Calabria	0,33	0,31	0,28	0,25	0,3
Sicilia	1	1,13	0,97	0,86	1
Sardegna	0,31	0,35	0,37	0,31	0,39

